

Graph-based algorithm for checking wrong indirect relationships in non-free choice

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ABSTRACT

In this context, this paper proposes a combination of parameterised decision mining and relation sequences to detect wrong indirect relationship in the non-free choice. The existing decision mining without parameter can only detect the direction, but not the correctness. This paper aims to identify the direction and correctness with decision mining with parameter. This paper discovers a graph process model based on the event log. Then, it analyses the graph process model for obtaining decision points. Each decision point is processed by using parameterised decision mining, so that decision rules are formed. The derived decision rules are used as parameters of checking wrong indirect relationship in the non-free choice. The evaluation shows that the checking wrong indirect relationships in non-free choice with parameterised decision mining have 100% accuracy, whereas the existing decision mining has 90.7% accuracy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Each company records events carried out in the event log. The analysis of information from the event log obtains the obtain knowledge [1]. The process of gaining knowledge from event log extraction is called the process mining, which aims to find out, monitoring and improving the processes that occur [2]. In the process mining, there are two most prominent processes, namely: 1) conformance checking [3] and 2) process discovery [4]. The process mining finds the wrong process in the event log. This paper discovers a graph process model based on the event log. The analysis of the graph process model obtains decision points. Each decision point is processed by using parameterised decision mining, so that decision rules are formed. The derived decision rules are used as parameters of checking wrong indirect relationship in the non-free choice.

Several previous studies discuss decision mining in recent years. A study conducted by Rozinat [5] explains decision mining on business processes. However, decision mining is not implemented as a decision rule for checking errors in event logs. Horita [6] made decisions on event logs that result in linear temporal logic, but the temporal logic is not applied for error searches in event logs. The existing methods in checking indirect relationships [7, 8] in non-free choice only using direction so the error can be detected only from directional error, but correctness from choosing directional cannot be obtained. The proposed method, namely parameterized decision mining is to use the decision rule in checking event logs with notice not only from

the direction but also the parameters in the event log. In this research, the decision rule is used to find errors in the event log, so the failure of event logs can be finding more accurate in terms of the direction and correctness of choice.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

In this section, parameterized decision mining will be presented to find a wrong indirect relationship in non-free choice using the graph database. The non-free choice is a condition that is not free to make choices, but choices depend on the results of the previous election [9]. Checking process models on the non-free choice part of the event log can be done correctly must consider all dependencies [10]. There are two types of dependence on the process of the model, direct dependence or referred to as direct relationship and indirect dependence or referred to an indirect relationship [7, 11, 12]. A direct relationship is a relationship or dependency that is directly between tasks. Conversely, an indirect relationship is a relationship or a dependence that is indirectly between tasks [13]. A graph database is a NoSQL database where is depicted in the form of graph [14-16]. Graph databases will form data as nodes and relations between nodes [15, 17]. The process mining is used to extract information from the event log to see business processes [10, 18, 19]. The process mining can be used to build a process model [16, 20-23]. Decision mining is used to study parameters that can influence the selection of grooves [24, 25].

Decision mining is used to find rules for branching from each decision point. By using a graph database, a decision point can be known from a node that has a xorsplit relation. The algorithm used in decision mining research is using the C4.5 decision tree algorithm [5, 26]. A decision tree is used to predict an activity seen from the parameters of a data. The decision tree has several terms. Those terms are a root as the initial node, a leaf node as the child of a node, and the depth of a node as the length of the path between the nodes to the leaf node [27, 28]. The first step is to discover graph process model of the event log based on the graph database. Then, graph process model be analyzed to find the decision point. The second step is discovering decision rule using decision mining from each decision point with notice parameter in event log. This decision rule will be used as a parameter in determining the wrong decision in non-free choice. The last step searches each case in the event log with the parameters stated earlier.

2.1. Discovery process model based on graph database

The first step for the discovery of the graph model process is to enter event logs like in Table 1 into the graph database using a query like in Table 2. The parameters in the event log used in the graph database are Case_ID, Activity, and Time. In the Table 2 shown queries in the graph database for: (1) Import all data in event log, (2) Import only unique activity, (3) create relation: sequence, xorsplit, xorjoin, andsplit, andjoin, non-free choice, and (4) get the decision point.

In the model process, there will be several relationships such as xorsplit [29], xorjoin [29], andsplit [30], andjoin [30] and non-free choice shown in Figure 1. Joint relations are a relation of the union from branching to split relations at the base of branching. The xor relation is a branching relation which means that the flow of the event log can only choose one of the entire branches of the event log. The and relation is a flow relationship that will do all events even though the different order. The results of working on queries in Table 2 produce the model process shown in Figure 1. After each activity is represented in the node, the next step is to make relations between nodes such as sequence, xorsplit, xorjoin, andjoin, andsplit relations, and non-free choice.

Figure 1. Examples of the process model

After the graph process model is formed. The next step is to determine the decision point by using the query in Table 2. Decision point is the node where branching of the process begins. In Figure 1 shows graph process model where containing the decision points in node A and node E. Node A is the base of member node B or node C. Node E is the base of branching node G and node F. furthermore, decision rule would be discovered by decision mining to find parameters each branching of each decision point.

2.2. Extracting a parameter in decision points

The decision point shown in Figure 1, there are two decision point points. Each decision point will be analyzed by considering the parameters in the event log to get the decision rule. The process for extraction decision rule is called decision mining. The algorithm of decision mining is used C4.5 decision tree algorithm. The first step is getting leaf nodes from each decision point. Then, the next step is getting an event log that has activities such as leaf nodes with algorithm in Table 3.

The data needed in algorithm in Table 3 is *decisionPoint*, *leafNode*, dan *eventLog*. Each decision point of leaf nodes obtained from algorithm in Table 3 is used in the decision mining process. The decision mining algorithm is seen in Table 4. Algorithm in Table 4 has five data variables: X is the event log on node leaf. Y is an attribute owned by X. The *splittingAttribute* is an attribute used as a solving parameter. The *attributeSelectionMethod* is the method used to find the best fraction value. The method used to find the best splitting criterion is C4.5 with the gini index parameter in (2) and (3). The function of (1) is to evaluate the separation in event log each attribute. The function of (2) is to evaluate the separation in event log each parameter.

$$Gini(t) = 1 - \sum [p(\frac{j}{t})]^2 \quad (2)$$

where $p(\frac{j}{t})$ represents the frequency of the j attribute in activity t.

$$Gini_{split} = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{n} Gini(i) \quad (3)$$

where k is the number of partitions, n_i is the amount of data in i partition, n is the amount of data in the p node. The best split value is indicated by the smallest $Gini_{split}$. The *splittingCriteria* is the value of the parameter that is used as a solver. N is a node. The algorithm in Table 4 will continue to be repeated until the data is X empty. The results of algorithm in Table 4 are a decision tree by showing the parameters and the leaf values can be seen in Figure 2.

Table 1. Process mining will be carried out by the event log

Case_ID	amount	stackType	Status	Time	Activity
PP10	3	nonreefer	complete	3/11/2016 0:52	A
PP10	3	nonreefer	complete	3/11/2016 2:00	C
PP10	3	nonreefer	complete	3/11/2016 3:08	D
PP10	3	nonreefer	complete	3/11/2016 4:16	E
PP10	3	nonreefer	complete	3/11/2016 5:24	F
PP10	3	nonreefer	complete	3/11/2016 6:32	H
PP412	17	reefer	incomplete	7/2/2016 22:28	A
PP412	17	reefer	incomplete	7/2/2016 23:36	C
PP412	17	reefer	incomplete	7/3/2016 0:44	D
PP412	17	reefer	incomplete	7/3/2016 1:52	E
PP412	17	reefer	incomplete	7/3/2016 3:00	G
PP412	17	reefer	incomplete	7/3/2016 4:08	H
PP735	13	nonreefer	incomplete	10/2/2016 10:52	A
PP735	13	nonreefer	incomplete	10/2/2016 12:00	B
PP735	13	nonreefer	incomplete	10/2/2016 13:08	D
PP735	13	nonreefer	incomplete	10/2/2016 14:16	E
PP735	13	nonreefer	incomplete	10/2/2016 15:24	G
PP735	13	nonreefer	incomplete	10/2/2016 16:32	H
PP1050	10	nonreefer	complete	12/30/2016 16:52	A
PP1050	10	nonreefer	complete	12/30/2016 18:00	B
PP1050	10	nonreefer	complete	12/30/2016 19:08	D
PP1050	10	nonreefer	complete	12/30/2016 20:16	E
PP1050	10	nonreefer	complete	12/30/2016 21:24	F
PP1050	10	nonreefer	complete	12/30/2016 22:32	H

Table 2. Queries in the graph database

No	Queries
1	<pre>def importActivityT (tx, fileName): tx.run ("LOAD CSV with headers FROM 'file://'+fileName+' AS line " "Merge (: Activity {CaseId: line. Case_ID, Name: line. Activity, Amount: toInt (line. amount), StackType: line. stackType, Status: line. status, Time: line. Time})")</pre>
2	<pre>def importCaseActivity (tx, fileName): tx.run ("LOAD CSV with headers FROM 'file://'+fileName+' AS line Merge (: CaseActivity {Name: line. Activity}) ")</pre>
3	<pre>def createRelationship(tx): # create sequence relation tx.run ("MATCH (c: Activity) " "WITH COLLECT(c) AS Caselist " "UNWIND RANGE (0, Size (Caselist) - 2) as idx " "WITH Caselist[idx] AS s1, Caselist[idx+1] AS s2 " "MATCH (b: CaseActivity), (a: CaseActivity) " "WHERE s1. CaseId = s2. CaseId AND s1. Name = a. Name AND s2. Name = b. Name " "MERGE (a)- [r: SEQUENCE]->(b)") # create xorsplit relation tx.run ("MATCH (bef)-[r]->(aft) " "WHERE size((bef)-> ())>1 AND size((aft)<--())=1 AND (size((aft)-> ())=1 OR size((aft)-> ())>1) " "CREATE (bef)- [: XORSPLIT]->(aft) " "DELETE r") # create xorjoin relation tx.run ("MATCH (bef)-[r]->(aft) " "WHERE (size((bef)-> ())=1 OR size((bef)-> ())>1) AND size((aft)<--())>1 " "CREATE (bef)- [: XORJOIN]->(aft) " "DELETE r") # create andsplit relation tx.run ("MATCH (aft1) <-[r]- (bef)-[s]->(aft2) " "WHERE size((bef)-> ())>1 " "AND size((aft2) --> ())=size((bef)-> ()) AND size((aft1) --> ())=size((bef)-> ()) " "AND not (aft1)- [: SEQUENCE]->(bef) AND not (aft2)- [: SEQUENCE]->(bef) " "MERGE (aft1) <- [: ANDSPLIT] - (bef)- [: ANDSPLIT]->(aft2) " "DELETE r, s") # create andjoin relation tx.run ("MATCH (aft1)-[r]->(bef)<-[s]- (aft2) " "WHERE size((bef)<--())>1 " "AND size((aft2) --> ())=size((bef)<--()) AND size((aft1) --> ())=size((bef)<--()) " "AND not ()- [: ANDSPLIT]->(bef) " "MERGE (aft1)- [: ANDJOIN]->(bef)<-[: ANDJOIN]- (aft2) " "DELETE r, s") # create Non-Free Choice tx.run ("match ()- [c: XORSPLIT]->(n) " "match (a)- [b: XORJOIN]-> () " "match (k: Activity), (l: Activity) " "where a. Name<>n.Name and k. Name=a.Name and l. Name=n.Name and k. CaseId=l.CaseId and k. Time<l.Time " "merge (a)- [: NONFREECHOICE]->(n)")</pre>
4	<pre>def printStartingNodeNonFreeChoice(tx): nodes = [] global nodeStartedNonFreeChoice for record in tx.run ("MATCH (p)- [r: XORSPLIT]-> () RETURN p. Name ORDER BY p. Name"): nodes. append (record ["p. Name"]) nodeStartedNonFreeChoice = np. unique (np. array(nodes)) return nodeStartedNonFreeChoice</pre>

Table 3. Algorithm for getting event log of leaf nodes each decision point

Data: <i>decisionPoint, leafNode, eventLog</i>	
Result: <i>Event log pada leaf node</i>	
No	Pseudocode
1	<i>DataLeaf</i>
2	<i>for each x of decisionPoint do</i>
3	<i>for each y of leafNode of each x do</i>
4	<i>for z of eventLog do</i>
5	<i>if activity in each z of trueEventLog equals with activity in y leafNode then</i>
6	<i>attach a event Log z to DataLeaf</i>
7	<i>end</i>
8	<i>end</i>
9	<i>end</i>
10	<i>end</i>

Table 4. Algorithm for extracting a parameter each decision point using decision mining

No	Pseudocode
1	Create Node N
2	if tuple in X are all of the same activity then
3	return N as a leaf node labeled with activity in X
4	end
5	if Y is empty then
6	return N as a leaf node labeled with majority activity in X
7	end
8	attributeSelectionMethod(X,Y)
9	if (splittingAttribute is discrete – valued) then
10	Y ← Y – splittingAttribute
11	end
12	for each outcome i of splittingCriteria do
13	let Xi be the set of data tuples in X satisfying the outcome j
14	if Xi is empty then
15	attach a leaf labeled with majority activity in X to node N
16	else
17	attributeSelectionMethod(Xi,Y)
18	end
19	end
20	return N

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Decision tree in: (a) node A, and (b) node E

From Figure 2 (a) it can be concluded that the condition for doing activity B is ((status = complete AND amount > 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount ≤ 9)). Whereas to do activity C it must be conditioned ((status = complete AND amount ≤ 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount > 9)). From Figure 2 (b) it can be concluded that the condition for doing activity F is ((status = complete AND amount > 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount ≤ 9)). Whereas to do activity G must be conditioned ((status = complete AND amount ≤ 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount > 9)). The next step is to check the event log with parameters that have been obtained previously.

2.3. Checking wrong indirect relationships

After finding these parameters, then looking for wrong indirect relationship in non-free choice. Checking is done in each case. This is because each case has different parameters. The goal is to find faults with precision far better than just using the direction of each case. Checking scheme for non-free choices containing indirect relations as in algorithm in Table 5. From the algorithm in Table 5, there are needed several parameters like decisionParameter and *EventLog*. The process will repeat as many cases as in *EventLog* and checking in case *i* with *decisionParameter*. If the process is not same with the rule, then the case *i* will be added in *IndirectRelationship*.

Table 5. Algorithm for checking indirect relationship in non-free choice

Data: decisionParameter, EventLog	
Result: IndirectRelationship	
No	Pseudocode
1	IndirectRelationship
2	for each case <i>i</i> of EventLog do
3	if case <i>i</i> parameter not equal with decisionParameter then
4	attach a case <i>i</i> to node IndirectRelationship
5	end
6	end

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The proposed method is implemented in 1199 cases in event log. The event log has many various of attribute in parameter like amount, stackType, status, and times as in Table 1. From the 1199 case activity, the results of checking using the proposed method can be seen in Figure 3. From Figure 3 (a) having the sequence of events $A \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F \rightarrow H$ is the sequence of events that are wrong based on the parameters and based on the order of non-free choice. Case_ID PP10 has several parameters, which value of parameter status is complete and in parameter amount has 3. In Figure 3 (a) shows after activity A goes to activity C is a correct but wrong decision after activity E goes to activity F.

Figure 3 (b) has the order of events $A \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow G \rightarrow H$ is the sequence of events incorrectly based on parameters due to incomplete and amount 7 status parameters. In decision parameters obtained from decision mining requires that it can pass activity C then conditions fulfilled ((status = complete AND amount 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount > 9)) and conditions for passing activity G must meet the requirements ((status = complete AND amount 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount > 9)). However, when viewed based on the order non-free choice is correct.

Figure 3 (c) has the sequence of events $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow G \rightarrow H$ is the sequence of events that are wrong based on the parameters and based on the order of non-free choice. Case_ID PP735 has several parameters, which value of parameter status is incomplete and in parameter amount has 13. In Figure 3 (a) shows after activity A goes to activity B is a correct but wrong decision after activity E goes to activity G.

Figure 3 (d) has the order of events $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F \rightarrow H$ is the sequence of events wrong based on parameters because complete status parameters and amount 3. In the decision parameters obtained from decision mining requires that it can pass activity B then the conditions fulfilled ((status = complete AND amount > 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount 9)) and the condition for passing activity F must meet the requirements ((status = complete AND amount > 8.5) OR (status = incomplete AND amount 9)). However, when viewed based on the order non-free choice is correct.

Accuracy of the existing method shows 900 case activity in *TP*, 188 case activity in *TN*, 111 case activity in *FP* dan zero activity in *FN*.

$$Accuracy = \frac{900+188}{900+188+111+0} \times 100\%$$

$$Accuracy = 0.907 \times 100\%$$

$$Accuracy = 90.7\%$$

The accuracy of the parameterize decision mining shows 900 case activity in *TP*, 299 case activity in *TN*, zero case activity in *FP* dan zero activity in *FN*.

$$Accuracy = \frac{900+299}{900+299+0+0} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = 1 \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = 100\%$$

Figure 3. The result of the process which contains wrong indirect relationship in Case_ID: (a) PP10, (b) PP412, (c) PP735, and (d) PP1050

4. CONCLUSION

The decision mining overcomes the correct flow in a direction but not in a parameterize direction. The parameterized decision mining considers parameters in the selection of grooves. This paper proposes a combination of parameterized decision mining and relation sequences to detect the direction and correctness. Firstly, discovering a graph process model based on the event log. Then, an analysis of the graph process model obtains decision points. The process of each decision point is using parameterized decision mining, so that decision rules are formed. The derived decision rules are used as parameters of checking wrong indirect relationship in the non-free choice. The accuracy of the parameterized decision mining reaches 100%. It means the proposed method can detect errors far more precisely than the existing method only get 90.7% accuracy.

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